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Gpr84 is a marker of the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease.

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We report here identification of the G-protein receptor molecule Gpr84 as a sensitive and specific marker of disease in the peripheral blood of humans with the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease. Gpr84 was likely to also be an indicator of disease severity, increasing with disease activity.

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Results

GSE186507
n=207 control whole blood, human
n=67 active disease, whole blood, CD, human

Gene ID
53831

p-value
1.13E-14

Gene
GPR84

Gene name
G protein-coupled receptor 84

Rank: 29/19521

Gpr84 was differentially expressed more than 99.9% of the human whole blood transcriptome in humans with CD with active disease when compared to that of healthy control individuals.

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Methods

We used R-based computational methods for this transcriptome-based discovery approach to identification of markers for unbiased detection of autoimmune and inflammatory disease.